

Extractive spectrophotometric determination of tungsten(VI) using 3-hydroxy-2-(2'-furyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran as a complexing agent^ψ

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An extractive spectrophotometric method is developed for the trace determination of tungsten. Tungsten(VI) forms a light yellow (1 : 2) complex with 3-hydroxy-2-(2'-furyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HFB) in acidic medium. The coloured species is quantitatively extracted into dichloromethane and absorbance is measured at 405–413 nm. The method obeys Beer's law in the range 0–2.3 $\mu\text{g W}^{\text{VI}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$ with molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of $4.88 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0038 \mu\text{g W cm}^{-2}$, respectively, at 410 nm. The method is free from the interference of Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Nb, Ta, Mo, U, Zr, Th, Ce, Se, Re, platinum metals and many other analytically important elements. The proposed system handles satisfactorily the analysis of several samples of varying complexity.

Recent survey of literature on the spectrophotometric determination of tungsten reveals that the existing methods¹ using binary complexes are generally time consuming, non selective and thus have limited applications for the reasons of low sensitivity and more complexity of procedures. In view of the above observations, it is considered of interest to study the complex formation reaction of tungsten(VI) with 3-hydroxy-2-(2'-furyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HFB) which gives not only a more rapid and highly reproducible method but also provides a highly selective and sensitive extractive spectrophotometric determination of tungsten in trace amounts.

Results and discussion

Effect of nature of acids on the absorbance of W^{VI} complex: Tungsten(VI) formed a light yellow complex with HFB in acidic medium which was quantitatively extractable into dichloromethane. The effect of different acids on the absorbance of the W^{VI} complex was studied at 0.2 M acidity and it was found that the absorbance decreased in the order $\text{HCl} > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{HClO}_4 > \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 = \text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$. Therefore, HCl was preferred for further work. The complex formed was not extractable in alkaline medium.

Effect of various organic solvents on the absorbance of W^{VI} complex: Various organic solvents namely dichloromethane, chloroform, 1,2-dichloroethane, benzene, toluene, isobutyl methyl ketone, isoamyl acetate, carbon tetrachlo-

ride, isoamyl alcohol, cyclohexane, ethyl acetate extracted the metal complex in the decreasing order. Hence, dichloromethane showing maximum absorbance was preferred as the extractant for the metal complex. A single equilibration of the aqueous phase with equal volume (10 ml) of dichloromethane under optimum conditions gave quantitative (100%) recovery of W^{VI} -HFB complex.

λ_{max} and stability of the complex: The absorption spectrum of the extracted species in dichloromethane showed that the absorption maximum was in the range 405–413 nm, where the reagent blank had minimal absorbance. In dichloromethane, the absorbance remained unchanged for more than 1 h.

Effect of concentration of HCl, HFB and equilibration time on the absorbance of the complex: The optimum values of other parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance were : 0.06–1.00 M HCl, 1.1–2.2 ml of HFB (0.1% in ethanol) and 15–45 s equilibration time for $\leq 23 \mu\text{g W}^{\text{VI}}$ per 10 ml aqueous volume (Table 1). The order of addition should be the same as per proposed procedure.

Beer's law range, molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and composition of the complex: The metal complex obeyed Beer's law in the range 0–2.3 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1} \text{ W}^{\text{VI}}$ and after that concentration, it deviated from linearity. The Ringbom plot between log ppm of tungsten and percentage transmittance showed the optimum concentration of the

^ψDedicated to our revered teacher and founder Head of the Chemistry Department, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra, the late Professor S. M. Mukherji.

Table 1. Effect of various parameters on the absorbance of the W-complex

HCl (<i>M</i>) ^a	0.02	0.04	0.06–1.00	1.10	1.20	1.40	1.60	
Absorbance	0.205	0.240	0.255	0.240	0.210	0.185	0.150	
0.1% HFB (ml) ^b	0.1	0.5	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1–2.2	2.3	2.5
Absorbance	0.020	0.160	0.240	0.250	0.255	0.265	0.250	0.210
Equilibration time (s) ^c	0	5	10	12	15–45	50	60	90
Absorbance	0.050	0.190	0.225	0.240	0.265	0.250	0.200	0.185

^aW^{VI} = 10 µg, HCl = variable, 0.1 % HFB = 1 ml, equilibration time = 30 s, solvent = dichloromethane; ^bHCl = 0.2 *M*, other conditions being the same as in (a) except for the variation in HFB concentration, also ^b3-hydroxy-2-(2'-furyl)-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran (HFB); ^c0.1 % HFB in ethanol = 1.2 ml, other conditions being the same as in (b) except for the variation in equilibration time.

metal ion to be 0.60–2.13 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 410 nm were $4.88 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0038 \text{ µg W cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The ratio of W^{VI} and HFB in the extracted species was determined as 1 : 2 by Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper² for a two phase system. This was further confirmed by the mole ratio method.

Effect of diverse ions : Under the optimum conditions of the procedure in 10 ml aqueous volume (mg amounts in parentheses), chloride, bromide, iodide, sulfate, sulfite, nitrate, carbonate, thiourea and dithionite (100 each); thiocyanate (90); ascorbic acid and hydrazine sulfate (80 each); sulfosalicylic acid (50); phosphate (30); citrate and acetate (10 each); tartrate and disodium EDTA (5 each); fluoride (0.01); H₂O₂ (6% w/v) and glycerol (0.5 ml each) were without effect. However, oxalate interfered seriously. Among the cations, Pb^{II}, Ca^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Bi^{III}, Hg^{II}, Al^{III} and As^V (10 each); Mg^{II} (9); Ba^{II} and Sr^{II} (8 each); Cd^{II}, Sb^{III}, Ce^{IV}, Cu^{II}, Se^{IV}, Mn^{II} and Be^{II} (5 each); Cr^{III}

and U^{VI} (4 each); Os^{VIII} (3); Th^{IV} (2); Cr^{VI} and Pt^{IV} (0.5 each); Ta^V (0.4); Zr^{IV}, Ag^I, Au^{III}, Fe^{III}, Ti^{IV} and Ir^{III} (0.1 each); Ru^{III} (0.09); Fe^{II} (0.08) and Pd^{II} (0.03) caused <1% error in absorbance. V^V, Mo^{VI}, Sn^{II} and Nb^V did not interfere in the presence of respective masking agents as described under the procedure.

Applications : The usefulness of the method was tested by the analysis of several synthetic (some of them analogous to minargent, platinoid, W-alloy, heat resistant steel, high speed steel and stellite No. 2) and reverberatory flue dust samples with satisfactory results. The proposed spectrophotometric method is highly selective and sensitive, free from the interference of a large number of metal ions especially, Ti, V, Cr, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Mo, U, Zr, Nb, Re, platinum metals as well as many other important elements. The reproducibility of the method was tested by performing ten sets of experiments while keeping the same (1 µg ml⁻¹) amount of W^{VI} each time. The standard deviation was found to be ±0.0014. The method compared favourably with the

Table 2. Comparison of the present method with other methods

Sl. no.	Aqueous conditions	Solvent (λ _{max} , nm)	Sandell's sensitivity µg cm ⁻² (Molar absorptivity dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Interfering metal ions
1.	W ^{VI} , 20% KSCN, 40% SnCl ₂ , 8–9 <i>M</i> HCl, colour development time 15 min ^a	Isoamyl alcohol (403)	0.012 (1.56 × 10 ⁴)	Hg ^{II} , Au ^{III} , Pt ^{IV} , Cr ^{VI} , Ni ^{II} , Co ^{II} , As ^V , V ^V
2.	W ^{VI} , 1 <i>M</i> H ₃ PO ₄ (vanadophosphoric acid) ^b	– (360–460)	0.33 (6.21 × 10 ²)	Bi ^{III} , Pb ^{II} , Th ^{IV} , Zr ^{IV} , Fe ^{III} , Cr ^{VI} , Mn ^{VII}
3.	W ^{IV} , 0.4 <i>M</i> catechol, pH 2.0, colour development time 2 h ^c	1,1-Diantipyriny1heptane in dichloroethane (440)	–	Al ^{III} , Ti ^{IV} , Sn ^{II} , Bi ^{III}
4.	W ^{VI} , stilbazogal I, acetate-acetic acid buffer, pH 4.9, colour development time 5–15 min ^d	– (520)	0.0049 (3.76 × 10 ⁴)	Al ^{III} , Cr ^{III} , V ^I , Cu ^{II} , Mo ^{VI} , Ti ^{IV} , Th ^{IV} , V ^V , Zr ^{IV}
5.	W ^{VI} , 1–1.5 <i>M</i> ethanol HCl, 4-(2,3-dihydroxyphenylazo)-3-hydroxynaphthalene-1-sulfonic acid ^b	Butanol (540)	–	Ga ^{III} , Al ^{III} , Sn ^{II} , Ge ^{IV} , Mo ^{VI} , Fe ^{III} , V ^V

Note

Table-2 (contd.)

6.	W ^{VI} , conc. HCl, SnCl ₂ , 0.5% dithiol (in amyl acetate), heat to 80°, wash the extract with conc. HCl, Mo ^{VI} separated as dithiolate from 1.9 M HCl before determination of W ^{VI} ^e	Amyl acetate (640)	0.0096 (1.92 × 10 ⁴)	
7.	W ^{VI} , 25% KSCN, 10 M HCl, 30% SnCl ₂ , 0.5% quinaldic acid, heat to 80°, colour development time 10 min ^f	Isoamyl acetate (405)	0.012 (1.51 × 10 ⁴)	Mo ^{VI} , Pd ^{II} , Ti ^{IV} , Re ^{VII} , V ^V , Pt ^{IV}
8.	Present method	Dichloromethane (410)	0.0038 (4.88 × 10 ⁴)	39 metal ions do not interfere

^aRef. 1, 3. ^bRef. 3. ^cRef. 1. ^dRef. 1. ^eRef. 1. ^fRef. 6.

Table 3. Analysis of tungsten(VI) in different samples

Sl. no.	Composition (mg)	W added µg	W found*	
			Proposed method (%)	Thiocyanate method
1.	Cu (0.1), Ni (0.1), Pb (0.06) ^a	10.0	9.9 ± 0.79	10.86
2.	Cu (0.6), Zn (0.25), Ni (0.15) ^a	10.0	10.0 ± 0.00	10.00
3.	Cu (0.15), Zn (0.08), Al (0.12) ^a	15.0	15.3 ± 1.25	14.78
4.	Fe (0.15), Cr (0.03), Co (0.03), Mn (0.01), Ni (0.01) ^a	20.0	19.8 ± 0.66	20.87
5.	Fe (0.06), Cr (0.002), V (0.001) ^{a**}	10.0	10.0 ± 1.36	9.56
6.	Co (0.12), Cr (0.08), Fe (0.02) ^a	20.0	19.9 ± 0.77	20.43
7.	Mo (0.1), Cr ^{III} (1), Nb (0.1) ^b	5.0	4.9 ± 3.03	5.22
8.	Zr (0.05), Ta (0.1), Os (1)	12.0	12.1 ± 0.66	12.17
9.	Pt (0.1), Pd (0.01), Co (1)	15.0	15.1 ± 1.25	15.65
10.	U (1), Se (1), Ce (1)	7.0	7.1 ± 1.10	10.00
11.	Sn (0.01), Ba (1), Th (0.5) ^c	10.0	10.1 ± 1.09	6.95
12.	Ru (0.01), Ti (0.01), Mg (1)	10.0	9.9 ± 0.79	10.43
13.	Reverberatory flue dust (100)	10.0	10.1 ± 0.79	9.56
		15.0	15.2 ± 2.62	14.78

*Average of triplicate analyses; mean ± % RSD (n = 3), **In presence of 100 mg sodium dithionite.

^aCompositions of sample nos. 1–6 analogous to Minargent, Platinoïd, W-alloy, Heat resistant steel, High speed steel and Stellite no. 2, respectively.

^bIn presence of 0.5 ml of 6% (w/v) H₂O₂ and 0.01 mg sodium fluoride. ^cIn presence of 0.01 mg sodium fluoride.

existing methods of tungsten determination (Table 2).

Experimental

A standard stock solution (100 ml) of tungsten(VI) containing 1 mg ml⁻¹ of the metal ion was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed amount (0.179 g) of sodium tungstate (L.R., C.D.H.) in distilled water and standardized by the oxine method³. Lower concentrations at µg ml⁻¹ level were prepared by suitable dilutions therefrom. Solutions of other metal ions were prepared at mg ml⁻¹ level by dissolving their sodium or potassium salts in deionized water or dilute acid. They were suitably diluted to obtain lower concentrations of the metal ions at µg ml⁻¹ level. Hydrochloric acid (A.R., Ranbaxy) 2 M was prepared by diluting 11.3 M

acid with deionized water. Dichloromethane (Rankem) was used as such. 3-Hydroxy-2-(2'-furyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HFB), m.p. 171° was synthesized by the literature method⁴ and dissolved in ethanol to give 0.1% (w/v) solution. A UV-Vis (Shimadzu 140-02) spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched glass cells was used for routine absorbance measurements and spectral studies.

Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing a tungsten(VI) solution with solutions of other metal ions in suitable proportions (Table 3). Reverberatory flue dust sample⁵ (0.1 g) from copper manufacture containing no tungsten was mixed with a solution of known tungsten content (1 mg) and dried in an oven. After fusion of the dried

dust sample with sodium peroxide (0.8 g), the leach was treated with 0.5 g sodium potassium tartrate, neutralized with concentrated HCl and adjusted to 2 M acidity in 100 ml final volume. Aliquots (1 and 1.5 ml) were taken for the determination of tungsten by the proposed method.

Procedure : To the sample solution containing $\leq 23 \mu\text{g}$ tungsten(VI) and other ions taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel were added 2 M hydrochloric acid (1 ml), 0.1% (w/v) HFB (1.2 ml) and sufficient deionized water to make up the volume to 10 ml. It was then equilibrated once with an equal volume (10 ml) of dichloromethane for 30 s. The layers were allowed to separate and the organic phase was poured over anhydrous sodium sulfate for removal of any retained water. The absorbance of the complex was measured at 410 nm against a similarly treated reagent blank and the amount of tungsten was determined from the standard curve prepared in an analogous manner.

For 0.5 mg V^{V} was added 100 mg sodium dithionite, for each of 0.01 mg Sn^{II} and 1 mg Nb^{V} was added 0.01 mg sodium fluoride and for 0.5 mg Mo^{VI} was added 0.5 ml of 6% (w/v) H_2O_2 , as masking agents, prior to the addition of HFB in 10 ml aqueous volume.

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